

A Study on the Impact of Formative Years on Intra-Millennial Differences and its Effect on Work Values

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Ramini Singh

Research Scholar, IFIM Business School, VTU, Bangalore

Dr. Shaji Kurian

Professor- HR, IFIM Business School Bangalore

Abstract

Millennials have been classified by researchers as those who are confident, ambitious, tech savvy, multi-tasking, impatient about their career progress, mobile in their careers and believe in work-life balance. Practically, all these characteristics cannot be found in every millennial who is born between 1980-2000. Some of these characteristics are contrasting by nature. This study aims to establish the fact that millennials themselves are a cohort of two sub-generations in themselves i.e. Early Millennials and Late Millennials and explore the intra-millennial differences. The study will throw light on the likelihood of dependence of work value on the nature of socio-political, technological and economic events witnessed by millennials in their formative years.

Keywords: Millennials, Early millennials, Late millennials, Intra-millennial difference, Impact, Socio-political, Technological, Economic, Formative Years.

Introduction

The Millennials (Strauss and Howe, 2000), or Generation Y (Johnson and Johnson, 2010) have become a focal point of study from last decade due to high number in workforce. The age boundaries of Millennials have been given diverse definitions in a series of studies, with the starting year ranging between 1976 and 1980 and the ending year ranging between 1995 and 2000 (Reilly, 2012; Meier et al., 2010). But for the purpose of this study, birth years ranging from 1980 to 2000 (Strauss and Howe, 2000) has been considered. There have been various research papers which have described the characteristics of millennials. In these research papers, millennials have been treated as a cohort or generation with same characteristics and work values (Beekman, 2011; Cekada, 2012). This is in contrast with the statement suggested by Kennedy et al. (2007). According to him, wide age group of people between 16 and 40 years old shows stunning differences mainly due to the increasing pace of societal and technological changes. This statement has been further supported by Mannheim (1952), Pilcher (1994), Schullery (2013) and Underwood (2007). They defined a generation as a group of people born within a specified birth year range who grew up in the same

historical and socio-cultural context, and shared formative life experiences, such as pop culture, economic conditions, world events, natural disasters, technology, and as a result developed core values that are different from those of other generations. Hence it will be irrational to generalize millennials as a homogeneous stratum across globe, as the influencing factors in each country and culture differs hugely.

Schwartz (1999) reported that work values differs country wise and hence different values have been seen in individual which indicates the role of socio-cultural values associated. Therefore, it can be assumed that work values will differ in case of an Indian culture too.

This study holds an important relevance for India as half of its population is aged less than 25 years old. As reported by NASSCOM (2013), IT industry in India holds almost 2 million millennials in its workforce. A six-month study of the millennial demographic in India conducted w.e.f. October 2009 by Steelcase Workspace Futures discovered them to be open minded and positive for their work and the future. With the work values of tech savviness, confidence, impatient, ambitious, they want to balance between core Indian values and western style of living. This study aims to explore the reason behind these work core values and its relation with the events that took place in the formative years of millennials.

Theoretical Framework

For studying the Intra-millennial difference, millennials have been divided in two groups: (1) Early Millennials - born between 1980 to 1990, and (2) Late Millennials - born between 1990 to 2000. The impact of socio-political, technological and economic events during the formative years will be studied individually on these two groups and then the impact will be correlated to their work values. The impact of important events is studied for millennials in US and Indian millennials.

Early Millennials: The socio-political events that took place during formative years of Early millennials particularly in US and India are studied. In US, infamous attack of 9/11 and election of first ever black president in American history were the major events. In India, major political turmoil after assassination of prime ministers Indira Gandhi and Rajiv Gandhi, Pokhran nuclear test and Kargil war of 1999. The technological events that took place were invention of world wide web, dot com bubble and in India, it was urbanization, globalisation and growth of IT companies. The economy landmark event was economic liberalisation by Mr. Narsimha Rao government in 1991 and worldwide economic recession of 2008 which affected Indian early millennials.

Figure 1 Theoretical Framework

Late Millennials: The socio-political events that took place during formative years of Late millennials were hunt of terrorists responsible for 9/11, Iraq and Afghanistan invasion by US Army. In India, events such as 26/11 terrorist attacks in Mumbai, win of BJP in Lok Sabha elections marked the socio-political events. On technological front, launch of I-phones, smartphones, high

speed internet were ruling the world. In India, many MNCs and BPOs opened up which led to huge opportunities. From the economy point of view, global recession of 2008 had a significant impact on the mindset of late millennials.

The study of these events will lead to the behavioural changes and psychological changes in early and late millennials which is further responsible for their work values such as being ambitious, impatient, collaborative in nature, tech-savvy, self-assured, individualistic, wants to balance work-life etc. Out of these work values, some are common in early and late millennials while some are different and found in either one of them. The work values which are different will show the existing intra-millennial difference.

Literature Review

Work values are an important consideration in the work place because they predict choices and actions (Rokeach, 1973), direct behaviour (Hitlin and Piliavin, 2004) and affect a number of organisation outcomes, such as judgement and decision-making, work effort, satisfaction, commitment and performance (Connor and Becker,1975;Frieze et al.,2006;Meglino and Ravlin,1998;Meyer et al.,1998;Shapira and Griffith,1990;Judge and Bretz,1992). This was also supported by Connor and Becker (1975); Roe and Ester (1999) who suggested that work values affect choices, attitudes and goals and are closely connected to motivation (Hitlin and Piliavin, 2004; Latham and Pinder,2005). Therefore, it becomes important to study the work values of millennials who according to NASSCOM (2013) are an important part of workforce.

A number of articles and papers have been published related to characteristics and work values of millennials. According to the reports of Pew Research Centre (2007) and Twenge (2009), millennials have been described with the terms such as self-assured, individualistic, self-confident and self-absorbed. They are also impatient about their recognition at workplace (Gursoy et al. 2008; Pew Research Center 2007; Ng et al., 2010) and have the tendency to switch jobs and careers (Gursoy et al. 2008; Remo 2006; Lancaster and Stillman 2002). Despite these traits which are not so positive, millennials believe in teamwork and are collaborative in nature(Deloitte 2009; Gursoy et al. 2008; Raines 2002). They are tech-savvy, multi taskers and prefers social connections (Balda and Mora, 2011), desire a work-life balance (Ott et al. 2008, Carless and Wintle 2007; Smola and Sutton 2002), are rule followers (Howe and Strauss 2003), civic minded and collaborative (Jacobson 2007; Raines 2002). These traits and work values are reported considering millennials as a cohort or as a generation.

But studies conducted by Pew Research Centre (2010) stated that in millennial generation, there are two sub- generations which can be categorised as a generation before the introduction of smartphones and economic recession and a generation after that. Although there is no clear indication in studies about the year of bifurcation. These studies also suggested that the work values cannot be common for all in a millennial generation because this generation have been through many socio-economic and technological events during their formative years so their work values are supposed to be different. These reports are sustained by studies conducted by Inglehart (1997) which states that socio-economic conditions influence generational difference in work values which is further supported by socialisation theory and scarcity principle. As per socialisation theory, socioeconomic conditions of an adult's childhood and adolescence influence his basic values. As per scarcity principle, those socio-economic conditions are more subjective which were in scarce during childhood days. Meglino and Ravlin (1998) also stated that unique socio-economic conditions during formative years decide the distinct work value of each generation which remain relatively stable throughout the lifespan of an individual. Further, Meglino and Ravlin (1998) and Kupperschmidt (2000) reported that value orientations which an individual inherit from the

socio-economic conditions of childhood remains stable throughout his lifespan and leads to each generation's feelings towards work or their expectations from work.

Research Method

This study is based on secondary research where the data is collected from literature reviews, articles and reports. This study also contains the viewpoints of author on the read articles and reviews. For studying Intra-millennial difference and their work values, millennials have been divided in two groups and named as Early Millennials and Late Millennials. The word Early and Late millennials do not find its mention in the literature. Although few reports mention about the term Old and Young millennials. Early millennials are the ones who are born between 1980 to 1990. Whereas, Late millennials are the ones who are born between 1990 to 2000. The events which marked their formative years are studied till 2010.

Data Analysis

The data collected is qualitative in nature and collected through literature reviews and articles. The author has tried to analyse the data by establishing a relationship between impact of events in formative years and work values. In this section, firstly the formative years of early millennials are studied and then its impact on work value is analysed. Similarly, the formative years of late millennials are studied and it is related with their work values. The study of events in formative years are carried out for the early millennialage group of 10 years (events in 1990s) to 28 years (last event of economic recession in 2008). For late millennials, the study of events starts from when they were 10 years old (year 2000) till they turned 28 years (year 2018).

Formative Years of Early Millennials

In India, early millennials have witnessed beginning of urbanization, economic liberalization, reformed policies by government, advancements in science and technology, growth in education sector, growth of IT companies and listing of Indian companies in Forbes global (Roongrengrnsuke, 2010; Erickson, 2009).

Socio-Political Impact

Socio-Lifestyle Differences in India: Early millennials have witnessed advanced technology free life until 1990. In the era before 1990s, there were black and white TV with few channels, landline phones and manual paper work in offices. They have spent their childhood by reading books, playing outdoor games, shopping in grocery stores and using public transport. Parents of early millennials had limited sources of income and had to work hard for basic amenities. Early millennials enjoyed staying in joint families and acquired the values and culture from their parents and grandparents at the same time getting acquainted with trends of western culture. As per Kripalani (1999), people of this generation admired values of Mahatma Gandhi and at the same time they were wearing jeans, enjoying MTV and fizzy drinks. So, it can be assumed that Early millennials were admirers of Generation X and Baby Boomers and followed the western trends too. Fernandes (2000) suggested this was the era when satellite channels made the entry and ended the monopoly of Doordarshan (DD) which was the only means of entertainment. These satellite channels were responsible for the growth U.S. television shows as well as Indian versions of American talk shows and game shows. This setup diminished as the urbanization begun. During urbanization, there was high influx of population from rural to urban cities in search of employment. This led to the base of nuclear families and women joining the workforce in order to support household expenditure.

Figure 2 Impact of Events on Early Millennials

Political Differences in India: Early millennials witnessed assassination of then Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi during their formative years. Political turmoil in country led to increased awareness about political parties and accountability in politics. There were demands for safety and empowerment of women, reforms in education across primary, secondary and higher education during 1990s. The public-school system expanded massively and there was emphasis on quality education. In 1998 Pokhran nuclear tests were conducted which pronounced country's status as a nuclear power which probably helped create greater hope amongst a large number of millennials in the future of the country. Then came the terrorist attack on World Trade Centre, USA on September 2001 known as incident of 9/11. This left whole world in shock and fear and left a lasting emotional impact on late teenage minds of early millennials according to Pew Research study in 2011.

Technological Impact

In 1990, the world wide web (www) was first tested. The year 1995 marked the birth of Dot com bubble which attracted large number of companies in software industry. These years were important for early millennials as they were in their teens and preparing themselves for their graduation. The development of web browsers and internet explorer made surfing the world wide web easier and user friendly. This was the time when e-mails became popular and people started using instant messaging for communicating. In late 1990s, people were able to afford mobile phones and internet on the go. This generation was attracted towards opportunities in the IT sector and were preparing themselves for the courses related to IT. Due to the technology boom, the country's college graduates were able to enjoy economic optimism. According to Hamm (2008), this group had hopes for vibrant job prospects unlike the generation of their parents and grandparents. Due to IT boom, they preferred computer related high paying careers. Many of them migrated from India to foreign countries for advanced studies and in search of high paying job. Globalization made these millennials liberal and less conservative unlike their parents.

Impact of Country's Economy

The factors such as globalization and IT boom boosted Indian economy and financial growth. Adding to this was opening of multiple MNCs and BPOs which created enormous employment opportunities in IT sector. Early millennials were benefitted with these prospects and got the exposure of global culture and western trends. As reported by Erickson (2009), India became a huge source of IT talent and by 2008 and 34 Indian companies got listed in the Forbes Global 2000 ranking.

Due to liberalisation, industrialisation and technology boom, economy was flourishing in 1990s but end of 2000s saw global economic decline and recession which affected the people all around the world. The great recession of 2008 posed a serious threat to the careers of early millennials some of whom were already part of workforce and others who were going to join soon. This period shaped the life choices, future earnings of millennials who were already doing job and changed the job priorities of those who were on the verge of joining. According to International Labour Office (2009) worldwide employment in financial sector decreased by 3,25,000 from August 2007 to February 2009.

As the news of dip in financial sector spread in, the stock market nosedived to a loss of more than 50% of its value between its 2007 peak and the spring of 2009. The loss in finance sector affected manufacturing and construction sector. The USA alone lost 2.1 million jobs in manufacturing and 1.8 million jobs in construction sector respectively (US Bureau of Labour Statistics). By 2010, due to cut back in the consumption of consumer goods, the labour market shed nearly 9 million jobs. For those who were in the age group of 17 to 27 years, the unemployment rate increased by nearly 8%. This was a frightful scenario for those who have finished their graduation and were about to look for work. The fresh graduates were already under the burden of debts which they have taken for their education. Many millennials who were already in the workforce lost their respective jobs and were unable to find jobs for quite some time. For fresh graduates, it was difficult to find a new job due to stagnant hiring in corporate sector. Due to the slow start in career, it took early millennials years to pay off their education loans and create wealth. Oreopoulos et al. (2006) reported that, graduates who received lower starting salaries incurred large initial earnings losses which persisted for over 10 years.

Impact on Work Values

The entire childhood of early millennials is influenced from the upbringing by their parents and technological advancements which they witnessed. According to (McGuire et al. 2007; Stauffer 1997), early millennials have seen their parents doing hard work at their work place and not caring much about work life balance. But by doing so, boomer parents missed spending quality time with their children. Realising the fact, early millennials were more towards maintaining work-life balance. With the changes happening in societal values, the outlook of females of early millennials also changed. Changes in social lifestyle built a sense of independence, confidence and ambition in women when they joined the workforce, which was missing in traditional set up. They became conscious of their civic rights and participated in the movements against female foeticide, patriarchy in the administration and equality in education. As reported by Kripalani (1999), social, economic, and political liberalization brought about a paradigm shift in people's thinking which allowed Indians to believe that making money was respectable. This generation of early millennials was technologically sound, able to browse many channels through cable tv, had ambition of earning money, buying all amenities. Economic slowdown in 2008 affected early millennials in terms of their psychological attitude towards stock market and housing sector. They became pessimistic about their future for some time and valued their current job and started saving money for their future needs.

Formative Years of Late Millennials

This section will cover the events which occurred from 1990 to 2010. The events in 2000s had a special impact on teenage years of Late millennials. As suggested by Mannheim (1952) and Ryder (1965), young adulthood is a critical time for generational identity formation. The formative years of late millennials were full of life changing events such as terrorist attack of 9/11 on World Trade

Centre, natural calamities all over the world, debut of smart phones and broadband connectivity, Mumbai 26/11 terror attacks, excellence in space science by launch of first manned space flight-commerce boom, strong comeback of BJP (Bharatiya Janata Party) to power after Lok Sabha elections.

Socio-Political Impact

This was the time when world was condemning terrorist attacks on 11th September 2001 and preparations were on for “War on Terrorism”. One of the strict responses against terrorism was invasion of Iraq and Afghanistan by US Army. The biggest and most publicised event related to that was secret mission to track Osama Bin Laden. In India, terrorists responsible for Mumbai attack were given capital punishment which marked as a landmark verdict in the history of India. Besides that, the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013 (Nirbhaya Act) was passed and fast track courts were established. The strict actions and formation of amendments and policies gave common man a sense of protection and fearlessness. They felt the need to give back to society by voluntary contributions and associating themselves with several NGOs. In late 2000s, open social agendas on abortion, LGBT rights came up in nation and prompted late millennials to look to it in a progressive way unlike early millennials. During this time, there were reports of natural calamities of earthquake, hurricanes, flood and drought in many countries. The scientific reports claimed that calamities are the result of past and present activities of human beings. These reports spread awareness in society and late millennials included conservation of environment and natural resources and clean energy solutions in their agenda.

Figure 3 Impact of Events on Late Millennials

Technological Impact

The birth period of late millennials marked dot com boom, advent of mobile phones and satellite channels. In their adolescence years, the technology kept on booming with high speed internet connectivity, laptops, notepads, tablets replacing the desktop system. For late millennials, connectivity with the world was the most important thing and they could not imagine even a day without mobile or internet. According to Oblinger (2003), millennials of this age were confident with all forms of technology such as mobile phones, PDAs, computers, dedicated game machines, and many more. For them, internet was like a magic wand which can help them in their school work, sending immediate messages and help to stay in touch with their friends. This was also reported by Pew Research Center, (2010) which stated that late millennials are extremely techno-savvy and believe

their use of technology sets them apart from other generations. It was the period when various social networking platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn also came into the picture. According to Childs, Gingrich, & Piller (2010), 96% percent on millennial generation belongs to at least one social networking site. These platforms were emerging fast and provided effective means of communication through voice calls, chat and video calls. At the same time these advancements in technology crippled them in terms of face to face interactions and soft skills.

Impact of Country's Economy

In the United States, clearly, the biggest catastrophic event was the financial turmoil that began in December 2007 (NBER, 2010). As reported by Bloomberg (2011), USA economy came to an abrupt halt with personal consumption expenditures bottoming out in April 2009. The Great Recession, which officially lasted through June 2009, was the longest since World War II (NBER, 2010). The global effects of the Great Recession continued with a debt crisis in the Eurozone. The rating company Standard & Poor lowered credit ratings in nine European countries. This downgrading led to a drop in stock markets and a loss in confidence in the Euro and the ability of the European Union to rescue Eurozone members in need (Kirkup, 2012). Graduating from college and entering the labour market in a recession had an impact on job prospects, starting salary, and lifetime income. Late millennials witnessed this period as a striving period for their seniors i.e. early millennials who witnessed better economic conditions during their formative years but faced the harsh realities when joined the workforce.

Impact on Work Values

Late millennials have witnessed the struggling period of early millennials with the economy, use of latest technology and the changing socio-political situations. All these events prepared them to be tough, confident and rational. The political turmoil and cross-country terrorism incited a new wave of patriotism. This affected late millennials psychologically and made them more compassionate towards society and nation. According to Spiro (2006) and Paul (2001) they felt responsible and capable for contributing to the solution of larger societal problems and taking part in meaningful social activities than establishing their own family which is often viewed as a distant, highly difficult endeavour by them. They showed interest by opting solutions of carpooling, planting of more trees, waste segregation, water harvesting, reduction of e-waste and plastics in their daily life. Late millennials were ready to work extremely hard but they were not ready to accept "useless" rules and thrived for instant gratification (Wilner and Robbins, 2001; Paul, 2001). At work place, late millennials were extremely tech-savvy and knew how to use all kinds of technological advanced tools. At work place, late millennials started preferring text messages, emails over face to face interactions. This in turn nurtured a non-traditional collaboration at workplace on daily basis. According to Szalai (2011), they rely more on virtual, culturally diverse communities outside of their family or neighbourhood for their emotional needs. The economic recession also had substantial effect on the sentiments of late millennials. The negative environment of economic recession made late millennials the "ME generation" (Twenge, 2006). For them loyalty and commitment to one organisation seemed like a fading dream as they saw early millennials getting laid off even after years of commitment in same organisation. They appeared to be more self-centric and pleasure seeking as compared to early millennials. They started believing the concept of living life in present. They valued quality of life rather than quantity of life and saving for future. At work place also, they expected the job to be psychologically satisfying and challenging rather than the routine job. Most of the late millennials also became sceptical about the concept of safe and secure job after global economic downfall. They started exploring other opportunities such as entrepreneurship so that they can work on their own terms.

Result and Conclusion

As reported by Pew Research Centre, generational cohorts allow the researcher to study the changes in the opinion, views and lifestyle of an individual over the time. These changes are the consequence of various social, economic and technological events that took place in the formative years of that individual. As per the study of literature done by author and various reports published by Pew Research Centre, Deloitte Inc., there happened to be notable events in the formative years of Early Millennials and Late millennials. These events have led to differences in the lifestyle and work values of Early Millennials and Late Millennials and hence they cannot be grouped under a single cohort of Millennials. This phenomenon was also observed by social psychologist Jean Twenge from San Diego University who said that there are notable differences between older and younger millennials and they are self-contained generations in their own.

Early Millennials

Early millennials were the group of people born in the period of 1980 to 1990. The oldest millennial will be at the age of 39 and youngest will be 29 years old at the time of writing this paper. Early millennials were the ones who have seen the world at the time of 9/11 terrorist attacks, tense situations of Iraq- Afghanistan war and various terrorist attacks in India. With these memories, they were quite sensitive and conscious of political turbulence these events caused and were polarized towards the political on goings in their respective countries. They are from the era where families used to stay together and spend quality time with each other. Therefore, in their adulthood Early millennials are more family oriented and want to achieve work life balance. This can be supported by the views of Spiro (2006), Wilner and Robbins (2001). They found that these millennials were ambitious for monetary success, but also wanted psychological success; they wanted to be unique and find satisfaction and happiness in life. All these summarise the millennials trait of civic mind and collaborative nature (Jacobson 2007; Raines 2002) which has come from the time where they have seen terrorist attacks on their country and people suffering from that. A study done by Harvard University Institute of Politics (2008), also supports that 60 % of millennials shows interest in public service and wants to give back to their community.

Early millennials have witnessed debut of Internet at their time. They were used to dial up-internet connection which was far from broadband connection of late millennials time. Early millennials know the importance of Internet in today's time but they are not addicted to it. They still prefer taking time out, calling family and friends and meeting them instead of maintaining virtual relationship on social networking sites. As per Deloitte India report of 2019, about 64 percent of millennials admitted that they would be physically healthier if their social media time is reduced.

Early millennials were the ones who faced the wrath of recession of 2008. Most of the early millennials were in workforce and had invested in stock markets. Due to recession, many of them got laid off and lost substantially in stock markets. This made them more cautious, sceptical and pessimistic about market sentiments. Most of them had a slow start in their careers which affected their future plans. Since their start was slow, so they stayed with their jobs till they reached stability. Millennials characteristics of being civic-minded, eco-aware, confident, conventional, optimistic, and socially conscious were summarised by Hewlett et al. (2009) which aptly correlates with the journey of their formative years.

Late Millennials

Late millennials are the group of people born in the period of 1990 to 2000. The oldest late millennial will be 29 years old and youngest will be 19 years old at the time of writing this paper. Late millennials come from the period where their childhood witnessed one of the most

infamous events of 9/11. Terrorism was at its peak in 2000s which was the adolescence period of late millennials. This made them strong headed and alert for the possible happenings in and around them. Late millennials stood firmly against the terrorism and believed that they can bring the change by conducting protests and actively participating in elections. Late millennials were also environment conscious which comes from the fact that they have witnessed quite a number of natural calamities. They were able to comprehend the cause of these natural disasters because of awareness created by environmentalists all over the world. This statement was also supported by Deloitte India report of 2019 which states that 27% of this generation are concerned about the climate change and want to protect the environment.

As per the reports of Pew Research Centre (2010), late millennials are extremely techno-savvy and believe their use of technology sets them apart from other generation. This is because the smartphones and broadband connection have evolved in the time of Late millennials. So, they have never seen world without mobile phones and internet connection. This technological advancement made them more strong, outspoken and opinionated. They are able to express their emotions through Twitter, Facebook and Snapchat. Late millennials also used these social networking sites to express their protest or favour for the events happening all over the world. The late millennials are so used to internet world that they have created a whole virtual family on internet. They are at ease with virtual talk but feel uncomfortable talking to people in real world.

Late millennials had a different experience of economic recession of 2008 as compared to Early millennials. The oldest late millennials were in school when recession hit the world. They believed that if they follow a set pattern of rules to study and graduate, they will get a job easily. But things totally changed after recession, getting a job was not that easier. This idea made late millennials more practical and they preferred changing their jobs rather than looking for stability. Late millennials were ready to work hard and overtime in order to get raise in their respective jobs. They were even ready to change their jobs if they found the profile interesting and highly paying. This is also reflected in Deloitte India 2019 report which says that 80% of the late millennials wants to be wealthy. Also, Indian Late millennials are more inclined to leave their current employers in the next two years. They are less inclined to stay beyond five years in their current jobs as compared to their global counterparts. This is supported by reports of Pew Research Centre (2010) which suggests that late millennials are ambitious. The effect of all these events are justified by the characteristics of late millennials reported by Howell LP et.al (2009) and Pew Research Centre (2010). According to them, millennials core work place values include online social connectedness, teamwork, free expression, close relationships with authority figures (as they had with parents), creativity, work-life flexibility, and use of technology. All these characteristics go well with the late millennials.

With all these small but profound differences we can say that it is not fair to blend both Early millennials and Late millennials into a single cohort of millennials. Both Early and Late millennials have acquired these differences because of the significant events which took place in their formative years. These differences are the possible reasons behind their behaviour at work place. Although the qualitative study has been conducted for this paper, there is a scope of quantitative analysis to study these intra-millennial differences in detail.

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